

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

In the third issue of this year, we are proud to present seven high quality papers on different topics in computer science. I'd like to use this opportunity to gratefully acknowledge the support of the members of our editorial board which is essential for the publication of all articles in this issue. Please allow me also to point you to our closer integration of social media intended to spread the papers to a broader community and to share your favorite papers with your peers.

Matija Cankar, Matej Artac, Marjan Sterk, Uros Lotric, and Bostjan Slivnik from Slovenia introduce in their work a new algorithm for resource allocation in large, heterogeneous grids. Enrique Canto, Mariano Fons, Francesc Fons, Mariano Lopez, and Rafael Ramos from Spain focus in their reported research on image processing and discuss a fast self-reconfigurable embedded system on Spartan-3. Pekka Kekolahti and Juuso Karikoski from Finland focus their research on probabilistic relationships of mobile service usage behavior applying a Bayesian Belief Networks. In the e-education domain, Angels Rius, Jordi Conesa, Elena Garcia-Barriocanal and Miguel-Angel Sicilia from Spain introduce their extensible ontology-based framework to specify processes in learning environments. In their collaborative research between Austria and Germany, Christin Seifert, Eva Ulbrich, Roman Kern and Michael Granitzer contribute in natural language processing by a text representation for efficient document annotation. Jorge Villalon from Chile and Rafael A. Calvo from Australia introduce in their research a decoupled architecture for scalability in text mining applications. Martin Stein and Andreas Geyer-Schulz from Germany focus in their research on the comparison of five programming languages in a graph clustering scenario.

Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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